

Comparative Utilization of Potentiometric Titration and HPLC Methods for Content Determination of Propranolol Raw Material

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Abstract This study describes an application and comparative evaluation of a HPLC and potentiometric titration methods to quantify the content of Propranolol in raw material. HPLC analysis were carried out using a C18 column and mobile phase composed of 1.6 g sodium lauryl sulfate, 0.31 g tetrabutylammonium dihydrogen phosphate, 1 ml sulfuric acid, 450 ml of water and 550 ml acetonitrile, with a flow rate of 1.8 ml/min and UV detection at 292 nm. The titration method of Propranolol was carried out using sodium hydroxide 0.1M as titrant and ethanol as solvent. The end point was potentiometrically determined. The content obtained by potentiometry is 100.49%, by HPLC is 100.01%. These results meet the required standard.

Keywords potentiometric titration, HPLC, content, propranolol, raw material

1. Introduction

In recent decades a lot of attention has been paid to the quality of pharmaceutical products entering the market. The major challenge for the pharmaceutical industry is to produce quality medicines, which require rigorous quality controls to maintain the quality, efficacy and safety of these products [1]. The accuracy and reliability of the analytical results are critical in ensuring quality, safety, and efficacy of pharmaceutical products. However, to ensure these criteria, the choice of appropriate analytical method is required [2]. Propranolol is a B-blocker, belongs to the chemical family aryloxypropanolamine used as an antihypertensive, anti-arrhythmic and anti-angina [3].

Figure 1: Chemical structure of propranolol [4].

This study describes an application and comparative evaluation of HPLC, and potentiometric Titration methods to quantify the content of Propranolol in raw material.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. HPLC Content Determination

A HPLC brand WATERS 2695 was used, the chromatographic conditions were regled at injection volume: 20 μ l, Flow: 1.8 ml/min, temperature: 25°C, Column: C₁₈ (5 μ m x 4,6mm x 250mm) and the wavelength λ : 292 nm. The mobile phase is composed of 1.6 g of sodium lauryl sulfate, 0.31 g of tetrabutylammonium dihydrogenophosphate in a mixture of 1 ml sulfuric acid, 450 ml water and 550 ml acetonitrile, the pH was adjust to 3.3. The SCR control and test solutions were prepared at 2 mg/ml [4,5].

2.2. Potentiometric Titration Content Determination

A potentiometer brand METTLER TOLEDO DL50 was used, titrant solution of sodium hydroxide 0,1M, potassium phthalate acid standard solution 0,1 M. The test solution was prepared at 5mg/ml in ethanol [4,6].

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. HPLC Content Determination

Figure 2: Control solution chromatograms of first and second injection

Figure 3: Control solution chromatograms of third and fourth injection

Figure 4: Test solution chromatograms of first, second, third and fourth injection

Table 1: HPLC Content Determination Results

Name	Retention Time (min)	Area Average (mAu.min)	Content (%)	Normes (%)
SCR	3.851	23345968.33	100	99-101
API_Sample	3.829	23347844.67	100.01	

According to the chromatogram, the retention time of propranolol hydrochloride is 3.85 min. Value close to that required by the European Pharmacopoeia. The content of propranolol hydrochloride anhydrous is 100.01%, it meets the required standard.

3.2. Potentiometric Titration Content Determination

Figure 5: Test solution titration Graphics

Table 2: Potentiometric Titration Content Determination

Assay Number	NaOH Volume (ml)	Correction factor	Content (%)	Average	Normes (%)
1	4.345	0.9758	100.33	100.49	99-101
2	4.379		100.95		
3	4.340		100.21		

The content of propranolol hydrochloride anhydrous is 100.49 %, it meets the required standard.

4. Conclusion

The evaluated methods showed to be adequate to quantify Propranolol Hydrochloride in raw material. The potentiometric titration doesn't require the use of a reference substance. The manipulation is rapid, but the error margin is important than the HPLC.

References

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